

MAIN CAUSES OF BORDER ISSUES IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Markaziy Osiyo mintaqasida bir necha yillardan buyon mintaqaviy hamkorlikka o'zining salbiy ta'sirini o'tkazib kelayotgan chegaraviy muammolarga bag'ishlanadi. Maqolada ushbu muammolarning kelib chiqish sabablari, mintaqa mamlakatlari o'rtasidagi integratsion jarayonlarga salbiy ta'siri hamda mamlakatlar ijtimoiy- siyosiy hayotidagi dolzarb ahamiyati chuqur tahlil etilib, mazkur masalaning o'z yechimini topishiga to'sqinlik qilayotgan omillar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: anklavlar, eksklavlar, delimitatsiya, demarkatsiya, chegara masalalari, xalqaro munosabatlar

Abstract: This article is devoted to border problems that have had a negative impact on regional cooperation in the Central Asian region for several years. The article deeply analyzes the causes of these problems, their negative impact on the integration processes between the countries of the region, and their current importance in the socio-political life of the countries, and the factors that prevent this issue from finding its solution are cited.

Key words: enclaves, exclaves, delimitation, demarcation, border issues, international relations

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена пограничным проблемам, которые на протяжении нескольких лет оказывали негативное влияние на региональное сотрудничество в Центрально-Азиатском регионе. В статье глубоко анализируются причины возникновения этих проблем, их негативное влияние на интеграционные процессы между странами региона, их актуальное значение в

общественно-политической жизни стран, а также факторы, препятствующие решению данного вопроса, цитируется.

Ключевые слова: анклав, эксклав, делимитация, демаркация, пограничные вопросы, международные отношения.

Introduction

Central Asian region consists of five countries of which people and nation are very close in terms of customs, traditions, lifestyle and religious beliefs for centuries. However, it is also the region in which countries are still not highly-cooperated with each other and there is no intra-regional regionalism and integration. Many reasons can be counted for that, but one of the most important and absolutely actual one – territorial and border issues cannot be rejected. It is widely accepted that national borders are a fundamental factor in determining the degree of tension or cooperation in relations between states and within a region as a whole (Moraczewska, 2010). Since achieving the independence there have been countless and repeated transboundary clashes in the former Soviet Central Asian republics because of ill-defined state borders.

But interestingly, why such problems are not being solved, what are the main reasons of that and what can be implemented in order to reach the integration of Central Asian countries? There are several reasons of transboundary conflicts which are important to note.

Methods

In this article the sufficient use of systematic, logical analysis and historical methods has been implemented.

Result and discussions

First of all, the national-territorial demarcation implemented in Central Asia in the 20-30s of the 20th century is the main and original cause of these problems.

Turkestan has long been the only abode and common homeland of the people of the Central Asian region. Indigenous people of the republics of Turkestan, Bukhara, and Khorezm have been very close to each other in terms of customs, traditions,

lifestyle, and religious beliefs for centuries. Turkic peoples: Uzbek, Turkmen, Karakalpak, Kazakh, and Kyrgyz, as well as the Tajik people, lived in each of the states on the territory of Turkestan. The people of the Turkestan region considered this land to be their only land, the original Motherland.

The idea that the people of the region are united has been passed down from generation to generation and is reflected in the social, political and practical activities of national leaders. However, such ancient Turkestan was oppressed by colonialists for many years. **(Hayitov & Rizayev, 2021)**

In the second half of the 19th century, the Russian Empire conquered Central Asia. Until the beginning of the 20th century, the region was in a colonial state as a vassal of Tsarist Russia. The October coup of 1917 in the empire and the arrival of the Soviets at the top of the government also had an impact on Central Asia. During this period, when the national-liberation movements of the local population in Turkestan intensified, the country was reoccupied by the "Red Army" and began to be formed as a Soviet region in the East under the leadership of the RSFSR, based on the ideas of socialism and communism.

Afterwards, the organization of the Turkish Commission dealing with Central Asian issues was established and in 1920, the chairman of this commission, Yan Ernestovich Rudzutak, put forward a proposal to divide the Turkestan ASSR into autonomous republics based on their national characteristics.

Undoubtedly, this proposal was very positively received by the center, and a number of works were started in this regard. The main goal of such a policy which was based on the strategy "Divide- and- conquer!" was that, by dividing the region into different parts, it was possible to manage it without difficulties.

In the national-territorial delimitation of Central Asia in 1924, the principle that Uzbeks, Tajiks, Turkmens, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs and Karakalpaks, who are considered to be native nations, are scattered throughout the cities and villages of the region, was not sufficiently taken into account. As a result, the national-territorial demarcation was carried out not based on the mentality and wishes of the local people, but by the order

and instructions of the "Center". Because of this, this event became very complicated and controversial, a new geopolitical wave of demographic problems arose, which later led to negative consequences. Where there is a large number and a large percentage of the population belonging to one nationality, the boundary line was drawn from that place, and the lifestyle of the nomadic and semi-nomadic population was not taken into account. After the clashes and conflicts began to take a serious shape, measures related to the redistribution of the territory of one province or region between the Republics and the official inclusion of enclaves in the list were used.

In this regard, the issue of national territorial demarcation is defined as follows in the work "Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development" written by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov: "National territorial delimitation was like a work which would put a mine that would explode at a certain time under the future inter-ethnic relations and processes between the peoples of Central Asia, which could explode in an emergency situation and cause various conflicts and tense situations (Karimov, 1997).

In fact, we have been witnessing the victims of mines exploding at this particular time since the beginning of the 90s of the 20th century, after the independence of the countries of the region.

During the period of independence, many national and ethnic conflicts arose in the regions where national territorial demarcation was implemented by the Soviet government. This, in turn, attracted the attention of many foreign research scientists and historians. One such historian, G. Popov, the former mayor of Moscow, gives important information about this issue in the book "Oshibka v proekte Leninsky tupik". In order to keep as much of the conquered lands as possible, the leaders of the Bolsheviks divided these territories into areas that would inevitably cause inter-ethnic conflicts. (ИЮНОВ, 2009) However, until the 20s of the 20th century, there were no such countries as Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in the territory of Central Asia. As a result of the national territorial delimitation, the borders between

these countries were drawn in such a way that inter-ethnic conflicts were foreseen.

According to Nick Megoran, when Soviet policymakers drew the demarcation lines they could not imagine that these lines would one day become real interstate borders (Belafatti, 2016)

To sum up, this national territorial demarcation was a well-thought-out political trick by the Soviet government for the Central Asian countries, the impact of which was strongly felt by the countries of the region during the past years of independence, and high-level practical measures are needed to eliminate it in the near future.

Secondly, a number of problems and disagreements in the use of water have been the cause of many conflicts between nations. If we look at the main reason of the border conflicts after the independence of the countries of the region, most of them are due to the wrong distribution of water resources among the population or misunderstandings between them.

We know that as a result of various climatic changes, clean drinking water is decreasing on the earth, and the need for it is increasing due to the increase in the world population.

In particular, the region of Central Asia is also considered to be a region suffering from water shortage. Considering the fact that the main source of income of the countries of the region is agriculture, the population of the region is increasing, and the available water sources are decreasing, this problem is really urgent.

At a time when the value of such water is equal to that of oil, and the need for it is increasing, the misallocation of water in the Central Asian region is due to the "deeply thought out" border policy of the former Soviet Union in the region. A number of conflicts are arising between neighboring countries, especially in the border areas.

As a result of the collapse of the Soviet Union and appearance of five new independent republics in Central Asia, many natural resources, including main watercourses, have acquired transboundary character. The uneven distribution of water resources in Central Asia resulted in an interdependence of the upstream and downstream countries. (Janusz-Pawletta & Gubaidullina, 2015) An annual cycle of

disputes has developed between the three downstream countries – Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan – that are all heavy consumers of water for growing cotton, and the upstream nations – Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. The downstream countries require more water for their growing agricultural sectors and rising populations, while the economically weaker upstream countries are trying to win more control over their resources and want to use more water for electricity generation and farming. (Central Asia: Water and conflict, 2002)

Most of the border disputes between the countries of the region are caused by various misunderstandings related to water: For example:

- 1) The border clash between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in 2021 over water use in the Batken region;
- 2) The border clash between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan in 2016 over water use in the Sokh enclave;
- 3) The border clash between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan in 2013 over water use in the Fergana Valley;
- 4) The border clash between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in 1999 over water use in the Isfara River;
- 5) The border clash between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan in 1999 over water use in the Sokh enclave;

Besides that some other clashes can be exemplified, particularly, in January 2014, at the water distribution point in the Botken district between the border guards of Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan the shooting that took place; Armed conflict between the military of Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan in April-May 2021; On May 31, 2020, in the village of Chashma on the Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan border, clashes between local people over the use of spring water.

In general, any action around water resources in the region has already become a major source of conflict, as it directly affects the interests and well-being of the population. In most of the countries of the region, the extremely low incomes of the population encourage people to maximize the use of land and water resources. A sharp

increase in water consumption in spring and summer, when agricultural work begins, increases the conflict between neighbors.

Thirdly, the lack of a legitimate basis, that is, the lack of a legal basis for the delimitation of state borders with almost all countries of Central Asia, which has passed all approval procedures, is one of the main reasons for these problems.

Two of the five Central Asian states, namely Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, have largely avoided the problems associated with territorial disputes and solved the basic problem of delimitation of their respective overland borders with other Central Asian neighbors, thus fully completing their legal registration. Turkmenistan signed the corresponding agreements with Uzbekistan (September 2000) and Kazakhstan (July 2001), while Kazakhstan settled this issue by signing the agreements with Uzbekistan (September 2002), Kyrgyzstan (December 2001) and Turkmenistan (July 2001). On November 10, 2017, on the sidelines of the Samarkand meeting of the Central Asian foreign ministers, the treaty on the junction points of the border between Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan was signed. In fact, according to Kazakh Minister of Foreign Affairs Kairat Abdrakhmanov, the document finalizes the border legalization process among these three states (Kazakhstan dogovorilsya s Turkmenistanom i Uzbekistanom o tochke styka granicy., 2017)

Glancing at the recent history, there have been almost no border disputes in Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan, it follows that the only solution to eliminate border disputes in the region is to clarify and legally formalize these borders.

It is known that the Republic of Uzbekistan borders all the countries of the region and is located in its center. However, we can say that the country has reached a mutual agreement on the border issue with almost all its neighbors. Uzbek-Kyrgyz border In particular, a common border was established on the initiative and political will of the country's leaders, and all border disputes were resolved on the relatively controversial Uzbek-Kyrgyz border.

It is known that the most turbulent border in the region is between Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan. We have been witnessing border disputes between these two countries

almost every month. Of the 970-kilometer border between Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, only 503 kilometers have been identified. Although there have been several attempts to reach an agreement between the state authorities, clarify the borders and legalize it, this issue still remains complicated.

The fact is that in solving the border problem, each country relies on its own resources, documents in its hands and, most importantly, its own principles. In determining the border line, both countries recognize the need to take the territories defined by the USSR as a basis. But at this point, another subtle aspect is revealed - the maps made in the first half of the last century, when there were no specific technologies, when the population did not live in these areas, and the importance of the border in general did not reach today's level, differ sharply from each other.

Tajikistan insists on the need to work on the basis of maps made from 1924 to 1939, while Kyrgyzstan says that the map made in 1959 is final. Naturally, even when these maps were being made, someone did not pay serious attention to them, and the people who made them had already gone to the immortal world.

Since then, almost every year, even several times in some years, there are shootings, blood is spilled, the parties meet, sit at the negotiation table. But there will be almost no change, there will be no political will, local conflicts will be "buried" for a certain period of time. (Zohidov, 2022)

To sum up, the border disputes between the countries of the region, which remain a topical issue today, taking into account not only the interests of the countries themselves, but also the interests of the neighboring countries, and first of all, the legalization of the borders, making it equally beneficial for the people living in these areas and legal determination can be the only solution. Most importantly, these boundary lines must also correspond to the location of land use, irrigation networks, infrastructure facilities, households and cemeteries in practice.

Fourthly, the current situation in the Central Asian region will, of course, be aggravated by the intervention of external forces and their direct or indirect influence. It is this factor that is considered the most terrible, dangerous and extremely important.

Undoubtedly, frequent border conflicts, unfinished delimitation and demarcation works, a number of enclaves and exclaves in the region, transboundary water resources and the policy of thinking first about oneself in their use hinder the integration processes in the Central Asian region and it is considered a factor that is increasingly delaying mutual economic, social and political cooperation, formation as a whole region in the world not just as an object, but as a subject.

And in the region, there are large power centers that have their own interests, and its unification can be very expensive for them, which cannot be denied at all.

We know that the Central Asian region has direct borders with China and Russia, two of the most powerful countries in the world. This means that the interests of the two countries directly intersect in this region.

Russia has been historically the pre-eminent power in Central Asia, having colonised the region during Tsarism in the nineteenth century and incorporated it into the Soviet Union after the Bolshevik revolution. In the twenty-first century, Russia's traditional dominance became increasingly challenged by China, so that Russia has been seeking to counterbalance a growing Chinese influence in the region.

When it comes to the interests of Russia and China in this region, Central Asian countries are the most vital exporters of fossil fuels and other regional reserves to the highly- developed, economically advanced, but at the time lack-of-natural-resource countries. Besides that, according to the conception of Sir Halford Mackinder called "Heartland", Central Asia's geography represents the world's most vital place, marking it as the pivot region of the world's politics. He asserted that command of this "Heartland" subsequently leads to govern of the entire world: "Who rules the Heartland commands the World-Island; Who rules the World-Island commands the world". Furthermore, Mackinder claimed that Eurasia contains an advantageous position. Also, the spatial signifies its notability and magnitude due to faster or easier, delivering the goods instead of ocean paths. He pointed out that the region can constitute the economic and military power as it can ascribe the significant control over the territory that means vital trade point. (Mackinder, 1919, p. 186)

So, Russia prefer that there is no any intra- regional cooperation in Central Asia sticking to its strategy “divide- and- conquer”. All in all, it can be said that one of the most important reason for the the failure of Central Asian regionalism and existing problems happening in the region like transboundary conflicts, is the pull of extra-regional actors, foremost Russia, which has torn the region apart.

As an fruitful example, as many political scientists have claimed that the conflict that took place on the border between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in the last days of September 2022, which caused the death of many innocent people, can be related to the “Uzbekistan-Kyrgyzstan-China” railway that was discussed at the SCO summit in Samarkand. To put it bluntly, having stronger relationships with other great power in the region cannot be accepted and interrupted by other one.

It is known that this region, made up of former Soviet countries, is still under the direct or indirect influence and pressure of Russia. The countries of the region, which are economically, socially and politically interconnected with Russia, still have to reckon with it in many aspects.

Not only Russia, but also major power centers such as China, the USA, Iran, and Turkey have the ability to influence certain countries of the region. This, in turn, may lead the countries of the region to pursue one-sided policies without considering mutual interests and delay the resolution of existing problems.

Conclusion

Since gaining independence, Central Asian countries have been making great efforts to achieve friendship and good neighborliness. They are trying to improve the connections and relationships in the spheres of economics, politics, culture and others with each other. However, the problems like bloody conflicts in the consequence of interethnic tensions and territorial claims are being one of the main cause to the fail of several integration initiatives.

Mutual relations between the Central Asian countries have always been difficult consisting of border incidents, trade bans, railway closures, gas supply cuts and even border mining.

However, in the recent years we can witness positive results that is strengthening the links among all countries in the region. Particularly, addressing of border issues, gradual improvement of intraregional relationships.

As a bright example of that, resolving the border issues between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan with an initiative of the presidents can be an another step to the improvements in the relationships in the region.

These days, another main issue has not been resolved yet, exactly, the border issues between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan still exist. The main causes of that has been counted above.

It appears that the most important strategic task for the Central Asian states is to ensure their unity which is based on their common historic, ethnic and cultural roots, as well as shared interests and challenges. (Mametova, 2019)

In that circumstance, the governments of the Central Asia states will have to be in progress to negotiate to resolve the long-standing issues between them.

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